

A Study On Work Life Balance Of Employee At The India Cements Ltd., Tirunelveli

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Abstract

The Study entitled as “ A Study on work life balance of employee at The India Cements Ltd., Tirunelveli” . Work–life balance is the lack of resistance among work and other life roles. It is the state of stability in which demands of individual life, specialized life, and family life are equal. Work–life balance consists of, but it is not incomplete to, flexible work preparations that permit employees to carry out other existence programs and practices. Work–life balance is a term normally used to explain the balance that a working person needs between time owed for work and other aspects of life. The aim of this study is to analyse the work life balance of employees in The India Cements Ltd.. This study help to find out what the employee feel about work survival balance, whether an employee is a privy to work life strength. From the findings, it is recommended that many of the respondents are satisfied with The India Cements limited and its work life balance of employees. So the company has to take required step for additional improvements than the past and more attention on the induction programmes to the new employees of the India cements limited.

INTRODUCTION

Work- Life Balances does no longer mean an the same strength. Demanding to agenda an identical diversity of hours for every of many paintings and private actions is usually difficult and impractical. Life is active and not fixed. Each individual’s paintings-existence balance will variety over the years, regularly on a day by day basis. The appropriate permanence for everyone these days will probable be unexpected from the day after today. The right balance choice while one is single and could be dissimilar at the same time as one marries or has an accomplice or if they have kids. When one start a new line of work as different to when one is nearing leaving bring changes in paintings-existence stability there’s no best, one size suit all, the stability that one ought to determined for.

Work family development refers back to the faith that concurrently accomplishing more than one work and own family roles and valuable for the physical and rational dating strength of people. The great of the jobs, as different to the measure of roles engaged or the amount of time exhausted in a particular site, make a decision the degree to which persons revel in the fantastic outcomes of participating in several roles.

OBJECTIVES

- To determine the fundamentals affecting paintings like balance
- To find out the centers provided by the company to the worker for balancing painting-existence
- To recognize the individual pleasure level in the direction of paintings and private lifestyles
- To analyse what are the power is supplying to the employee for corresponding work-existence.

NEED OF THE STUDY

- To recognize whether work lifestyles stability makes better crew work and excellent communiqué among worker and reduce strain to the worker in the organization work.
- To realize approximately painting life stability is crucial for enhancing the moral amongst employee in the organization
- To realize how work life balance will boom in the work flexible and element time operating styles. How work lifestyles balance will boom in work flexible and element time operating styles.
- To take a glance at about paintings competence is rising during the work-lifestyles balance

Research Methodology**1. Research Design**

Descriptive research is adopted to particularly afraid with the explanation of the attribute of a selected individual (or) a collection. This study consists of surveys and fact-locating enquires of the different type. The primary motive of descriptive research is the report of the situations, as it exists as a gift.

2. Area of the Study

The questionnaire is conducted among all category of employee who are working in The India Cements Limited Tirunelveli.

3. Sample Size

The Sample size taken in this study is 120 respondents

4. Data Usage

The study is conducted both primary and secondary data

5. Period of the Study

The study was conducted for the period of October and November 2019

6. Sample Technique

Simple random Sampling method was adopted.

7. Tools for analysis

The collected data is analyze with the help of statistical tools like simple percentage method, Chi-square test and likert scale.

CHI SQUARE TEST**AIM**

To test the significant difference between marital status and satisfied with my holiday shopping with my family.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between marital status and holiday shopping with family.

Alternative Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant relationship between marital status and holiday shopping with family.

Table -1

S.N	Marital Status	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dis-satisfied	Highly Dis-satisfied	Total
1.	Married	9	9	10	6	1	35
2.	Single	20	10	45	9	1	85
	Total	29	19	55	15	2	120

Table -2

Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (F)	O- E	(O -E) ²	(O -E) ² / E
9	8.45	0.55	0.30	0.03
9	5.54	3.46	11.97	2.16
10	16.04	-6.04	36.48	2.27
6	4.37	1.63	2.65	0.60
1	0.58	0.42	0.17	0.29
20	20.54	-0.54	0.29	0.01
10	13.45	-3.45	11.90	0.88
45	38.95	6.05	36.60	0.93
9	10.62	-1.62	2.62	0.24
1	1.41	-0.41	0.16	0.11
			Total	7.52

Therefore the calculated value of $\chi^2 = 7.52$. the tabulated value of χ^2 is 9.488

Since the tabulated value of χ^2 is higher than the calculated value of χ^2 . We understand the null hypothesis is 5 percent significance level. Hence there is the significant relationship between marital status and holiday shopping with my family.

Table - 3

No	Particulars	Respondent's Response					Likert Scale		
		S.A	A	N	D.A	S.D.A	Weighted Score	Total score	Percentile points
1.	Family matter reduce the time you can contribute your job	38	32	08	24	18	408	600	68
2.	Family worries or troubles redirect you from your work	42	26	14	23	15	417	600	69.5
3.	Family activities stop you receiving the amount of sleep you need to do your job good	37	21	18	20	24	387	600	64.5
4.	Family obligation decrease the time you require to quiet down or be by yourself	28	37	14	23	18	478	600	79.67

As per the above calculation family obligation degrees the time you require to quiet down or be by yourself getting 79.67 percentile points followed by family matter reduce the time you can contribute your job 68.

LIMITATIONS

- Due to time restraint the sample size was reduced to 120
- The judgment of the respondents may be prejudiced.
- The respondents are busy in the work
- The staff are busy in their work.
- Judgment is completed only based on questionnaire

SUGGESTIONS

From the analysis and interpretation made and the finding listed out the following suggestion have been given by the researcher.

- Factors influence work life balance of the respondents
- Time management is one of the best solution to decrease inequity between work and family obligation.
- Management could carry out time management training of their employees
- Many employees would desire to reduce working days, because the employee are working 6 days in a week and do not get time for individual development.
- Respondents are frustrated towards the safety requirements, therefore intense concentration should given to it.

CONCLUSION

Work and personal life are the two sides of the similar coin. It refers to those factors which hit a balance between work, family and self. In our study area many workers are fulfilled towards their present job and family life. But the same time put into practice like target fixing, working hours, force of work, stress etc.. Cause them imbalance. Therefore the company can provide have amusement activities like entertainment is to help reduce their worry and revive their minds. I conclude my study the employees in the study do not find sufficient with their family, so the company can offer members to participate in special occasions and the respondents do not use adequate time for amusement activities.

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